

Neoliberal Governmentality and Discourse Analysis of Interviews. Mothers' Stances on Freedom of School Choice

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Abstract

While from a neoliberal governmentality approach, school choice encourages families to behave as consumers of education, interview-based research has nuanced this explanation by uncovering the tensions experienced by mothers. Based on these contributions, this article provides a theoretical-analytical framework specifically designed for interview analysis to capture the contradictions faced by mothers in the process of school choice. This framework combines the governmentality approach with a set of tools from discourse studies. Throughout this paper, we deploy this framework on interview fragments with mothers and fathers whose children attend public schools in Madrid. Thus, a secondary objective of this work is to present three different types of stances taken by mothers toward school choice, as revealed by these interview fragments.

Keywords: school choice; mothers; neoliberal governmentality; discourse analysis

Introduction

'Freedom of choice' has been a key motto of neoliberal discourse since Milton Friedman intensely publicized it during the 1980s in written works (Friedman & Friedman, 1980) and through the television program *Free to Choose*. Reinforced by the Public Choice Theory, highly influential in the USA (Brown, 2019; Fraser & Jaeggi, 2018), this motto currently permeates both

political discourse and everyday vocabulary. In the field of education, it has spread globally hand in hand with school choice policies, which are part of the privatizing reform agendas promoted in the era of neoliberal capitalism (Lubienski, 2006). While the USA and the UK might be seen as paradigmatic cases (Butler & van Zanten, 2007), the vast literature on school choice reflects its expansive character. Dixon and Humble (2019) compile case studies in Liberia, Sweden, United Kingdom, and India. Seppänen et al. (2015) reveal its adaptability to disparate contexts by comparing the extreme cases of Chile and Finland. Along the same lines, Zhou, Mau and Jordan (2020) find that even in China, where enrolment is organised by zonification, choice is a frequent practice for families. This body of work reflects the hegemonic character of school choice, and especially its ability to permeate educational 'common sense' even in settings where choice is not promoted by the state.

Within this large body of literature on school choice, we can distinguish several lines of enquiry from critical perspectives. (1) Numerous articles have insisted on the correlation between freedom of parental choice and segregation/inequality (Ball et al., 1996; Bellei et al., 2019; Maroy, 2008; Yoon et al., 2018). Much of this research consists of geographically-oriented studies that intersect with the area of urban studies, given the revelation that school choice is an eminently urban problem (Wilkins, 2010, 2014; Yoon et al., 2018). (2) A second line of research has focused on how competence rationality is introduced through school choice policies, thus, inviting schools and families to guide their practices according to the model of the *entrepreneur of the self*: schools develop marketing practices typical of the business world (Angus, 2015; Fernández González, 2022; Jabbar, 2016; Jabbar & Wilson, 2018; Lubienski, 2006; Maroy, 2008; Prieto y Villamor, 2012), while families are invited to behave as consumers of education (Jódar & Gómez, 2007; Olmedo & Wilkins, 2016). (3) From the Bourdieusian perspective, research has focused on how families deploy differentiated choice strategies based on their social class and cultural capital (Ball, 2006; Ball, et al., 1996; Reay et al., 2011; Reay & Ball, 1997; Yoon et al., 2018). Thus, while the critical sociology of education of the 1970s highlighted the reproductive

function of schools (Baudelot & Establet, 1970/1987; Bourdieu & Passeron, 1970/1977; Bowles & Gintis, 1976), these studies point to the reinforcement of this reproductive logic because 'when mothers and fathers and guardians make decisions about where their children will attend school they enter into a relationship with schooling institutions known for inequitable organizational structures and practices, as well as unequal educational opportunities' (Oría et al., 2007, p. 91). Within this line of research, it is worth highlighting those studies that, based on interviews with fathers and mothers, highlight the dilemmas and contradictions they face when making school choices. These studies have illuminated relevant nuances by showing that families do not behave as harmonious consumers of education, but rather that choice generates significant ethical conundrums for them (Oría et al., 2007; Reay et al., 2011; Wilkins, 2010, 2014).

Against this theoretical background, this article provides an analytical framework drawn on the governmentality approach and specifically designed to trace in interviews the ambivalences experienced by mothers¹ in the process of school choice. As Barnett *et al.* (2008) indicate, the majority of governmentality studies focus on materials such as policy documents or interviews with elites (e.g., policymakers) as they aim to investigate how policy *invites/encourages/fosters* subjects to conduct their conduct according to neoliberal rationality. However, as we have just mentioned, research in the field of school choice and families is marked by an ethnographic approach developed through interviews. Only this approach has been able to show the tensions experienced by families. In light of this, our framework innovatively combines the explanatory strength of the governmentality approach with an interview analysis aimed at capturing the tensions that mothers, fathers, and guardians reveal in interviews. In this article, we will deploy this framework on qualitative data generated through interviews with 15 mothers and 5 fathers

¹ To make visible the feminised nature of rearing tasks, including school choice, we refer only to mothers in the title of this chapter, as well as in the sections' titles. Furthermore, 15 of the interviewees were mothers, while only 5 of them were fathers.

whose children attend public schools² in Madrid. In this way, the secondary objective of this work is to present three different types of mothers' stances (Du Bois, 2007) toward school choice. Each of these stances is constructed based on a specific type of tension in relation to the choice. These tensions reveal that neoliberal governmentality does not operate as an infallible rationality over subjects, but interacts in diverse ways with other political rationalities. The Madrid case is particularly relevant because, governed for over twenty years by conservative forces, constitutes a paradigmatic scenario within the Spanish context of neoliberal education policies (Ramírez Aísa, 2016).

The article is structured as follows: firstly, we present our object of study, the policies of freedom of school choice in the Community of Madrid, which we analyse through the lens of the governmentality approach. Secondly, we explain the methodological and analytical considerations of this research. Thirdly, we use excerpts from the interviews to show the three types of stances (Du Bois, 2007) we have identified in the discourses of the mothers interviewed. We close the article with a discussion section where we gather our overall conclusions.

School Choice in Madrid: The Neoliberal Governing of Public School

The notion of 'freedom of choice', popularized in the 1980s, provides a good illustration of the novelties of neoliberal governmentality compared to classical liberalism. In his 1978 lectures, Foucault (2008) clarifies the distinction between liberal governmentality and neoliberal governmentality. The former is configured in the eighteenth century as a distinction from agenda: the problem of liberalism 'was to distinguish between actions that must be taken and actions that must not be taken, between domains in which one can intervene and domains in which one cannot intervene' (Foucault, 2008, p. 133). This agenda distinction points to the core issue of interventionism: where the state should act and where it should not. Neoliberals,

² Unlike in other countries, such as the UK, in Spain, the term 'public schools' refers to formal educational institutions that are funded and operated by the state, providing free education to students.

however, will break with this agenda distinction by proposing the expansion of market rationality—the law of supply and demand and rationality of competition—to all spheres of life: to the state sphere as well as the intimate lives of individuals through the theories of human capital (Laval & Dardot, 2013). In this respect, the technology of ‘freedom of choice’ conveys just such rationality as it ‘presupposes that subjects are led by an “invisible hand” to make the choices that will be advantageous to each and every one of them’ (Laval & Dardot, 2013, p. 267).

While freedom of school choice has been promoted by liberal positions postulating the necessary existence of non-state educational options (see for instance Llorent Bedmar, 2004), neoliberal discourse promotes it by claiming that a ‘milieu’ of competition among schools will increase educational quality. In words of Milton Friedman, ‘giving parents greater choice had a major effect on education quality’ (Friedman & Friedman, 1980, p. 173). Faithful to the reasoning of Friedman, Lucía Fígar, Madrid's Minister of Education between 2007 and 2015, stated the following:

Freedom of choice rather than just an end, is a means to improve overall results of the system. The logical explanation is that when there is freedom, when there is competence, when there is autonomy, when forces and creativity are released... overall quality improves³.

This faith in self-regulation as *The way* to maximise quality replicates the magical thinking of the invisible hand within the field of education. Nonetheless, academic research has consistently refuted this theory: certainly, school choice unleashes competition among schools, but there is no confirmed relation between this competition and quality of education. Setting aside the very thorny issue of the meaning of ‘quality’ and its neoliberal roots (Fernández González & Monarca, 2019), numerous studies insist on the relation between parental choice and school segregation (Ball et al., 1996; Bellei et al., 2019; Maroy, 2008; Yoon et al., 2018).

³ Translated from Spanish by the author(s) of this paper. See original speech here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4a2yvYn5OLs>

Focusing on the issue of competence rationality, studies in diverse contexts have revealed that choice policies drive schools to develop different types of strategies to face competition, such as marketing, branding, cream-skimming, and curriculum specialisation (Angus, 2015; Jabbar, 2016; Jabbar & Wilson, 2018; Lubienski, 2006; Maroy, 2008). In the case of Madrid, research has also observed these strategies (Fernández González, 2019; Hidalgo McCabe & Fernández González, 2019; Prieto & Villamor, 2012). These entrepreneurial dynamics aim to attract, not only more students, but also the 'best' students, which reflect the thread of continuity between neoliberal governmentality—that is, the extension of competence rationality to areas previously not governed by it, such as public schooling through school choice policies—and the dynamics of segregation/inequality (Fernández González, 2022).

On the side of the families, governmentality-based studies pose how school choice policies *summon* parents to adopt a model of consumer behavior. In this vein, Jódar and Gómez (2007) explain, in the form of an essay, that neoliberal governmentality reshapes school relationships through the lens of market logic. Based on a policy discourse analysis drawn on genealogical enquire and governmentality approach, Olmedo and Wilkins (2016) argue that school choice policies in England *summon* parents to adopt a model of citizenship that dovetails with the consumer model.

In accordance with Barnett et al.'s (2008) observations on the governmentality approach, these two studies unveil the way school choice policy '*aspires* to bring about certain subject-effects' (p. 629) over parents. But they do not grasp whether it actually manages to conduct their behaviour according to this rationality. Let us recall, as pointed out by Dean (2015), that the aim of Foucault's work 'is not seeking to access the complexity of everyday life but the conditions under which we form a knowledge of and seek to govern such domains as everyday life' (p. 359). That is why these works do not account for the multiplicity of rationalities that coexist with neoliberal rationality, as Dean (2015) indeed claims. Thus, the value of these works is to identify

how market rationality is introduced into the educational field through school choice policies, with the aim of reaching families.

In this scenario, ethnographic studies with interviews have provided relevant nuances. They have consistently revealed that, in the daily life of school choice, neoliberal rationality coexists with other rationalities, giving rise to important ethical dilemmas among families between choosing based on an individualistic criterion or making a choice committed to the community (Oría et al., 2007; Reay et al., 2011; Wilkins, 2010, 2014). Thus, these studies show that, although the consumption model that extends neoliberal governmentality is one of the rationalities at play, families do not behave harmoniously as consumers.

Parental choice policy has been progressively promoted in the Community of Madrid by the successive right-wing governments of the Popular Party (henceforth, PP) over the last twenty years. In 2005, *Order 1848/2005* regulated school enrolment by establishing a system of extended zonification. Note that 'admission' was the keyword in the title of this 2005 regulation. Its purpose was to guarantee an enrolment process aimed at equity. In 2012, *Order 2939/2012* extended the zones of influence, thus also broadening the range of options from which families could choose. Finally, in 2013, *Decree 29/2013* on 'freedom of school choice'—a term included in its title—was enacted. This decree took a definitive step forward by adopting 'freedom of choice', instead of 'admission', as the object of regulation. It eliminated zonification of the city into individual school districts, establishing the entire region of Madrid as one single school choice zone, known as '*zona única*'. This succession of regulations, as well as the words of the former Minister of Education, Lucía Figar, quoted above, reveal that school choice has been a central vehicle for introducing neoliberal governmentality into public schooling in Madrid.

The promotion of freedom of choice is part of a broader set of typically neoliberal policies promoted by right-wing governments of the PP in Madrid, which has governed the region since 1995. These include: (i) standardised assessments, which were accompanied by rankings of

results in the early stages of the policy; (ii) the promotion of ‘*colegios concertados*’⁴—private schools that are publicly financed, most of which are Catholic; (iii) the introduction and expansion of bilingual English-Spanish programmes within public schools, which is inspired by human capital and entrepreneurial perspectives on education (Hidalgo McCabe & Fernández González; 2019); (iv) and budget cuts in public education, specially in 2011.

Neoliberal Governmentality and Discourse Analysis of Interviews

Our study is embedded within the *critical policy sociology* current (Ball, 2006; Regmi, 2017). Rejecting positivist, functionalist, and technocratic views, *critical policy sociology* tackles educational policy as a space of interpretation, resignification, and conflict. To this end, it taps into the contributions of discourse studies, ethnography, and a governmentality approach, among other critical and poststructuralist contributions (Regmi, 2017). Consistent with this research current, we understand ‘critique’ in two senses. Firstly, from a Foucauldian perspective, we understand it as an exercise of ‘problematization’ (Foucault, 1995) aiming to interrogate the naturalised character of the rationality of competence that invites parents to behave as consumers of education—through school choice in our study case. Secondly, following Nancy Fraser (in Fraser & Jaeggi, 2018), we pose that critical research must map the social fault lines provoked by capitalism through the situated experiences of those who embody these contradictions. Considering freedom of choice at the core of neoliberal capitalism, parents’ contradictions before school choice are a sample of daily life contradictions engendered within neoliberal capitalism. Thus, in this research, we have addressed their experiences through ethnographic interviews. To explore the contradictions experienced by our interviewees, our strategy of analysis throughout the phases of our study—including the phase of writing this paper—has

⁴ The network of ‘*colegios concertados*’ was established in the 1980s. Madrid is one of the Autonomous Communities where these centres have greater presence. In the 2021-2022 academic year, 29.5 % of pupils attended ‘*colegios concertados*’ (Comunidad de Madrid, 2021).

been to trace the tensions provoked by the technology of school choice in their discourse, as we understand choice as part of the capitalist governance of the school in the neoliberal phase.

This article is based on semi-structured, comprehensive interviews () with 15 mothers and 5 fathers, which were carried out by [researcher name anonymised] between 2017 and 2018. The elaboration and analysis of the interviews have met the required ethical research protocols: the participants gave their written informed consent to participate, the interviews were audio-recorded, and their anonymity was preserved throughout the study. The names of the participants and school centres used in this article are pseudonyms. In addition, prior to the interviews, this study received a positive report from the Research Ethics Committee of the University [name anonymised].

The participants were interviewed about their practices and stances in relation to freedom of school choice in Madrid. They were recruited according to the criteria of Gradual Selection (Flick, 2009), which is frequent in Grounded Theory. Rather than designing a previous sample, we looked for the maximal variation during the fieldwork in order to 'integrate only a few cases, but those which are as different as possible' (Flick, 2009, p. 122). Thus, we included mothers with different income levels, located in different areas of Madrid, and whose children attended public schools with different characteristics (primary and secondary, low, and high enrolment, bilingual and non-bilingual). As it was a critical case, we interviewed mothers and fathers from a secondary school (*Kairós* Secondary School) that was closed by the decision of the Regional Ministry of Education on the grounds of low enrolment.

We cluster the interviewees in three groups. In the first group we include mothers/fathers of upper-middle class: these parents have tertiary studies, work in professional and white-collar jobs, live in high-income areas —most of which are recently built neighbourhoods— and their children attend public schools in those areas. A second group of mothers/fathers live in medium-income areas and consider themselves middle class. They also have tertiary studies, and they all show great concern with educational and rearing issues. Most participants in the second

group work in white-collar and pink-collar jobs. In the third group we include those mothers/fathers that define themselves as working-class. They live in medium income neighbourhoods and primarily work in the service industry or other blue-collar jobs.

Following Martín Criado (2014) and Martín Rojo & Molina (2017), our analysis of the interviews has intentionally traced the contradictions in the discourse of the participants. To do so, we have deployed three main analytical tools: *neoliberal governmentality*, *frame analysis* and *stance taking analysis*.

Neoliberal governmentality, which is our first tool, defines both a type of rationality of government and a grid of analysis: 'what I have proposed to call governmentality, that is to say, the way in which one conducts the conduct of the men, is no more than a proposed analytical grid for these relations of power' (Foucault, 2008, p. 186). As an analysis grid, it is useful to trace the rationality of competition in the discourse of the interviewees in order to determine the extent to which their reflexivity is guided by it.

Our second tool of analysis is *frame analysis*. There are several formulations of the concept of 'frame'. In this research, we have drawn upon the work of George Lakoff, who defines the frames as 'mental structures that shape the way we see the world' (2004, p. xv). Lakoff insists that frames are part of our cognitive unconscious, so all our mental concept unconsciously remit to certain frame to articulate our common sense. In short, every word evokes a frame (Lakoff, 2006). In this vein, in the interviews we observed that school choice immediately a market frame: the participants evoke the rationality of competitiveness by employing market vocabulary, such as 'offer', 'supply', and 'marketing'.

Lastly, we combine *frame analysis* with *stance taking analysis* (Du Bois, 2007; Martín Rojo & Molina, 2017), a sound tool for conversational and interview analysis. Rather than an elicitation technique, we understand the interview as an interaction between the interviewer and the interviewee. Throughout this interaction, both participants evaluate whilst describing the objects they are talking about; that is, they take a stance in relation to both the object and other people's

stances about that object. Participants' alignment with other's stances may shift throughout the interview. Furthermore, when participants intervene in the interview, they are not only taking a stance in relation to the other participant, but they are also taking a stance within the broader discursive/ideological context. Thus, this tool makes our analysis an ideological analysis (Martín Rojo & Molina, 2017). Drawing on this tool, in the following section we provide a classification of three distinct stances toward choice. These stances illustrate the non-linear character of neoliberal rationality, as school choice does not transform mothers into harmonious consumers of education.

In a complementary way, we used three additional tools from Discourse Analysis (*interdiscursivity* and *chain of equivalences*) and Interactional Analysis (*face-work*) to give a more detailed analysis of some interviewees' stances. Let us briefly explain them. Considering that all texts are the result of the interaction between various prior discourses, the notion of interdiscursivity designates this interaction (Fairclough, 1993). Thus, a study of interdiscursivity aims to identify these prior discourses. For example, in our interview analysis, we have paid attention to the various discursive rationalities that weave their stances. The second tool is the notion *chain of equivalences*. Laclau and Mouffe's discourse theory (1985) poses that signifiers acquire their meaning relationally with other signifiers, through chains of equivalence and difference. Thus, through political discourse, political forces anchor highly abstract terms, such as justice or freedom, to more specific ones, such as wealth distribution or market. In this way, discourse is constructed through chains of equivalences. For example, the neoliberal discourse constructs the following chain of equivalences in relation to school choice: freedom = freedom of school choice = families' right = educational quality (Fernández González, 2019). Finally, the third tool is the notion of 'face-work'. Goffman (1967) defines 'face' as 'the positive social value a person effectively claims for himself by the line others assume he has taken during a particular contact' (p. 5). Therefore, 'face-work' refers to the strategic actions developed by a person throughout an interaction aimed at preserving their own positive image.

Mothers' Stances on Freedom of School Choice: The Tensions of Neoliberal Governmentality

Ambivalence in upper-middle-class mothers: 'the shame of choosing'

Research that uses interviews (Oría et al., 2007; Reay et al., 2011; Wilkins, 2010, 2014) has revealed the ambivalent tensions experienced by parents in their school choice practices. Some of these works have focused on middle-class parents (Reay et al., 2011). As these works reveal, school choice positions them in the dilemma between making a community-committed choice or making an individualistic one, the latter of which is what neoliberal governmentality dictates. Throughout this section we will share the stances of two interviewed mothers that dovetails with this type of dilemma.

Paloma, a mother of two children with tertiary education, works an office job. She lives with her husband and their children in Pozuelo de Alarcón, a municipality in the north of Madrid with one of the highest average incomes in Spain. Paloma and her partner used to live in downtown Madrid before they decided to move to Pozuelo when they had their first child. Their decision was driven by the more homogeneous social composition of public schools in Pozuelo. Paloma explains their decision in the following excerpt:

Excerpt 1. 'A public school in a good neighbourhood'⁵

Paloma: We put that decision at the centre of where to live and everything. Maybe it's a bit dramatic ((she laughs a bit)) but that's how we did it. I suppose each family does it in a different way. And then we considered what I was saying before: public, private and so on, and then we looked at the cost involved and what it implied in terms of educational style and so on, some institutions and others and... in the end what we decided was that we

⁵ The interviews were conducted in Spanish. The excerpts gathered in this article have been translated to English.

wanted a public school in a good area where there might not be so many problems,
maybe...

Interviewer: mhm mhm

Paloma: this is a bit snobbish but that's how it is ((she speaks in a lower volume)).

In this extract of her interview, Paloma reproduces a cost-benefit calculation for each option, considering various criteria —the economic costs (*‘the cost involved’*), the *‘educational style’* and the *‘problems’* the school might have. Through the cost-benefit analysis, which reflects a style of reflection typical of neoliberal governmentality, Paloma takes responsibility for her decision. As a result of her evaluation of options, she explains that they opted for *‘a public school in a good area’* to avoid *‘problems’*—so they moved to Pozuelo. It is worth noting her stance (Du Bois, 2007) in relation to her own decision. Far from any neutral, she is repeatedly self-critical: her behaviour is *‘maybe a bit dramatic’* or even *‘a bit snobbish’*, as she states in a lower volume reflecting a certain embarrassment. Formulating this self-criticism is also an exercise in honesty for her: perhaps she is a bit of a snob *‘but that's how it is’*, she says sincerely. Throughout the interview, she insists on her self-criticism, as we see in the following excerpt 2, where she makes more explicit what she understands by the euphemism *‘problems’*:

Excerpt 2. ‘Immigration problems, violence issues’.

Paloma: Just like didn't want a public school in a neighbourhood with a very high percentage of immigration because it implies certain problems, we believe that a private school with a certain social class has other problems, also bad ones, that we didn't want. So that's why we're happy with the school we're in, to be honest.

Interviewer: What problems do you associate with each of the two?

Paloma: Well, this is very... there are many... this is pure prejudice, I mean, it's not something rational... well... issues of non-integration, that form, for example, the most marginal... neighbourhoods, because of... little integration between the families of certain groups with the rest... and also between the rest with them.

Noelia: mhm

Paloma: and then problems... economic problems or dysfunctional families that lead to certain... problems, and issues of violence... which, I repeat, is a prejudice, maybe a very big and unfounded one, but... it's... at the end of the day, you make decisions, sometimes with information and sometimes with prejudices, and so that, issues of violence, economic problems, certain criminality and so on, and then, I don't know, what I was saying earlier, right? of sometimes behaviour in the classroom that can unbalance a classroom and...

Noelia: mhm

Paloma: That on the one hand, and then on the other, well, other problems, different ones, of... values that we don't share, of priorities in life, of certain things, of money or... I don't know, and other problems that... we haven't really spent much time with either one part of society or the other.

By using the term '*problems*', Paloma builds two opposing alterities and places herself in a middle ground between them, as middle-class. At one pole, she represents the school reality of working-class neighbourhoods as problematic, with higher levels of migration, which she quickly associates with '*violence*', '*criminality*' and, therefore, with '*behaviour in the classroom that can unbalance a classroom*'. Although she recognises her stance towards these schools as a prejudice ('*pure prejudice*'), she explains that they moved to Pozuelo to avoid this context. On the other pole, they wanted to avoid private schools, which they judged as elitist and frivolous ('*values that we don't share*', such as '*money*'). Like in excerpt 1, Paloma is self-critical: perhaps she is prejudiced ('*pure prejudice*') or even very prejudiced (a '*very big*' prejudice) in associating public schools in poor neighbourhoods with immigration-violence-criminality-distorted families. With her insistent self-criticism, Paloma manages to construct a positive self-image—what Goffman (1967) calls 'face work'—as a person with a sensitivity to inequality and is therefore not entirely satisfied with her decision. Finally, in order to keep this positive image, she justifies her decision pragmatically ('*at the end of the day, you make decisions, sometimes with information and sometimes with prejudices*'), placing her prejudices and the information on an equal footing, thereby justifying her own behaviour. As

Martín Criado (2014) points out, people often make up excuses to resolve their inconsistencies or to provide an outlet for their ambivalences, and this is the way in which Paloma ultimately resolves her dilemma with herself.

In the discourse of Lucía, another of the mothers interviewed, this same ambivalence emerges, albeit with greater intensity. She works as a civil servant and is the mother of two children. She lives in Las Tablas and her children attend the public school near her home. Las Tablas is a newly built area in the municipality of Madrid with a high average household income (€59,000 per year, whilst in the Community of Madrid is €35,500, according to INE⁶ data from 2019) and where mainly young families live, so it has a high school-age population, causing some public schools to be overcrowded. In line with Paloma, Lucía also identifies the neighbourhood and the social composition of its residents as a crucial aspect:

Excerpt 3. 'You don't want it happen to your child'.

Lucía: it's true that public education in some neighbourhoods may have a... greater integration component that we didn't want to face at that time, and we didn't have to face because we didn't... The public schools in Las Tablas are schools where all the children are practically the same in...

Interviewer: so... if you had been for example in another neighbourhood, like... I don't know...

Lucía: if we had been...

Interviewer: Vallecas, Lavapiés?

Lucía: if we had been in Lavapiés we probably wouldn't have taken him to a public school, probably not.

Interviewer: mhm

⁶ Instituto Nacional de Estadística (*Statistics National Institute*). <https://www.ine.es>

Lucía: because I would have had to suffer the consequences of integration, which is great, but when you have a child, you don't want it to happen to yours. You want it to happen to... you want it to happen in general, but you don't like it to happen to yours.

Several years before having her first son, Lucía used to live in Lavapiés, a neighbourhood downtown known for its intercultural character. Unlike Paloma, Lucía did not move to Las Tablas with school issues in mind —she insisted several times in the interview that she did so because she wanted to have a house with a swimming pool. At the same time, however, she recognises that she would not have taken her children to a public school in neighbourhoods like Lavapiés or Vallecas. In this excerpt 3, the object that Lucía is evaluating (Du Bois, 2007) is not choice, but integration. Thus, one of the critical issues in school choice studies emerges: ethnic segregation. She describes integration as a feature without agency (*'a component'*), that just magically happens (*'you want it to happen in general'*), and to which she is ambivalent: she is in favour of it (*'it's great'* she says) when she frames it in abstract terms, but evaluates it negatively when framed (Lakoff, 2006) in the logic of her choice as a mother: *'but when you have a child, you don't want it to happen to yours'*. Immediately following, she is about to continue by saying *'you want it to happen to...'*, but self-censors before finishing the sentence *'you want it to happen to others'*. This self-censorship reflects a certain amount of embarrassment about her way of thinking. We thus see that the technology of choice leads Lucia to look at interculturality from an individualistic and selfish prism justified by a mother's love for her children and the consequent fear of their suffering: the verb *'to cope with'* denotes her fear of integration, frequent among the middle classes in their strategies of choice (Ball, 2006). In the following extract 4, Lucía verbalises this ambivalence more starkly:

Excerpt 4. 'I can move to Galapagar'.

Interviewer: What do you think about school choice policies?

Lucía: I think it's terrible, to be honest, because... they leave us parents... what I'm saying to you, I'm a bit embarrassed, you know? I'm saying this so that you can use it in your

research, speaking frankly, it puts you in the situation that I'm moving to Galapagar for a school, you know? you can't say that since, in connection with this debate... obviously, it's terrible if a public representative is saying it, but it's what all parents do privately. It is legitimate from a private point of view, but from a public point of view, it shows 'unas fauces horrosas',⁷ because what it does is create educational ghettos, because I can move to Las Tablas, but not everyone can move to Las Tablas.

Interviewer: mhm

Lucía: And I can move to Galapagar, but not everyone can move to Galapagar, so integration is not real. Ghettos are formed, and... of course, from a private and selfish point of view, well, the last one is a rotten egg, you know?

Interviewer: mhm

Lucía: because we can do it. If we couldn't do it... it would be different. I think that it discriminates a lot against lower incomes.

In this extract Lucía's stance about freedom of choice is blunt: '*I think it's terrible*'. Revealing a high level of awareness of how choice is a technology of government, she rejects the individualistic and selfish behaviours that are naturalised through school choice. To this end, she uses as an example the case of the leaders of the political party Unidas Podemos, Irene Montero and Pablo Iglesias, who decided to move to Galapagar, justifying their decision, among other reasons, because they wanted their children to attend a public school in Galapagar well known for its innovative teaching methods. For Lucía, this is '*selfish*' and classist behaviour ('*not everyone can move*') that generates segregation ('*ghettos are formed*'). Although Montero and Iglesias intended to publicise their commitment to public education, Lucía believes their behaviour naturalises a selfish competitive race where '*the last one is a rotten egg*'. She also dislikes that this kind of behaviour is being proposed as an example in the public sphere ('*it's terrible if a public representative is saying it*').

⁷ '*Unas fauces horrosas*' translates literally to '*horrific jaws*', which is a metaphor used to refer to a tragic reality.

By using this example, Lucia reproduces the antinomy between *public* and *private*. On the one hand, '*the private point of view*', that of the passions; where the maternal instinct proves to be crudely selfish (the metaphor of the '*unas fauces horrosas*' evokes a wild maternal protecting instinctive), but still legitimate. On the other hand, from the point of view of the public, governed by the principle of equality, Lucia understands that choice '*discriminates against lower incomes*'. Through this antinomy, she makes visible the dilemma in which she feels enmeshed, oscillating between her identity as a mother and her identity as a citizen. It is a dilemma resulting from the interdiscursivity —the confluence of different discourses (Fairclough, 1993)— within which she is subjectified: between neoliberal discourse and social democratic discourse. While social democratic discourse gravitates around the concern for school equality, neoliberalism pushes mothers towards making selfish choices that interpellate their passions and fears as mothers.

Paloma and Lucía share a stance towards school choice marked by feelings of shame and guilt. These feelings reveal that school choice policy does not require the full conformity of mothers to guide their conduct in an individualistic way. It is not necessary for mothers to believe in the benefits of school choice advocated by Milton Friedman or Lucía Figar, because choice places them in a situation of individual responsibility, from which other rationalities are activated such as motherly love, and fear of their children's suffering, closely linked to a racist logic of fear of migrants. These converging rationalities activate a behavior similar to that of a consumer in the sense that it is also individualistic. Their ethical affinity, which does not correspond to the motivations of their respective school choices and is close to the rationality of the social-democratic discourse, is what triggers their feeling of shame and guilt. Thus, we see how interdiscursivity, in which various discourses and their rationalities converge, challenges and elicits a contradictory and ambivalent feeling that takes the form of guilt and shame.

'School choice is a lie': no supply, no choice

A second stance (Du Bois, 2007) is identified in parents who see freedom of choice as an unfulfilled promise. In this case, it is not an ethical dilemma in their process of subjectivation like the one experienced by Paloma and Lucía. Here, Chema and José identify a contradiction in the technology of choice itself: although neoliberal discourse promulgates freedom of choice, they consider it to be a lie as long as a plurality of options is not guaranteed. Thus, they take a stance against the way school choice actually takes shape in Madrid.

Chema, like Lucía, lives in Las Tablas, and has three children who attend public school. He actively participates in the 'Plataforma por la Defensa de Centros Educativos Públicos de Calidad' (in English, '*Platform in Defense of Quality Public Schools*') which, in line with social democratic principles, denounces the overcrowding and poor infrastructure of public schools and demands increased funding. This platform blames the Madrid government of the PP for this situation. In the following excerpt, Chema points to the lack of public funding as the factor that prevents freedom of choice:

Excerpt 5. 'In an overcrowded school you don't have a place'.

Chema: having a 'zona única'⁸ is the ability for families to choose any school in Madrid.

But that is a lie. Because if you have a saturated, overcrowded school, you don't have spots there, that is, so, this year alone, fifteen thousand children didn't get their first choice. We got the data from Comisiones Obreras.

Chema's arguments are the result of the interdiscursivity (Fairclough, 1993) between the social democratic discourse —where he calls for more funding— and the neoliberal discourse —where he favours school choice. With his reference to data provided by the trade union, Comisiones Obreras ('Workers Commission' in English), one of the largest trade unions in Spain, he is also taking a stance within the broader ideological/political context of the Madrid region (Martín Criado, 2014): he is aligning himself with left-leaning political forces and

⁸ This refers to the single school choice zone. See page 8 for a description of this and other related policies.

opposing right-wing parties, particularly the PP government in Madrid. Through his reasoning, he is pointing out that by not guaranteeing school infrastructures, the PP government fails to make freedom of choice effective. At another point in the interview, the interviewer brings up the issue of school choice again, to which Chema responds bluntly:

Excerpt 6. 'I am in favour of freedom to choose, but it has to be real'.

Interviewer: So you're telling me that, that it's important that... that families can choose according to their...

Chema: yes, yes, yes, yes, yes, yes, yes, yes, yes, yes. I mean, freedom of school centre must be real. Of course, I am in favour of freedom of centre, but I want it to be real, of course, that is... say I, for example, want to ask for a place in Montecarmelo I get a place in Montecarmelo. Because for me, for example, maybe it's because of a family situation, for example... that is, there are many factors around, things around... I could never say 'Freedom, hey, no, no, not freedom of centre, you assign me to this centre here', hey, no. Maybe your child, or maybe your family... has a specific background or a specific speciality and want to pass it on to their child, and they don't have to go through a private centre, for example.

Interviewer: mhm

Chema: I mean, you can't force me to go to a private school, I mean, you give me the option to go to a public school, it's in there with the rest, but, I mean, give me the freedom to choose a school⁹. I don't have it. I don't have freedom in my decision because I don't have a choice.

When asked for his opinion, Chema is emphatically in favour of freedom of choice (eiven 'yes'), insisting, however, that it must be '*real*'. Angrily, he launches his claims against a government that he considers is not guaranteeing it: '*give me freedom to choose a school*'. Immediately following, he deploys his arguments in favour of the principle of plurality: he understands that the public network must provide a response to all the preferences of families, whatever they may

⁹ Underlining indicates that these words were uttered with greater intensity.

be, because *'maybe your family... has a specific background or a specific speciality and want to pass it on to their child'*. This explanation is articulated through the principle of tolerance, which allows him to replicate the ideological grammar of pluralist liberalism, according to which all individual choices are equally legitimate and should be tolerated (Žižek, 2008). In this discursive grammar we identify the neoliberal governmentality (Foucault, 2008), which dilutes education as a collective issue and configures it as an individual-familial matter. The requirement to be tolerant of each individual-familial choice, whatever it may be, makes it illegitimate to discuss collectively. This argument echoes the Thatcherite motto *'There is no such thing as society. There are individual men and women... and their families'* (quoted by Brown, 2015, p. 100). In this way, education is privatised in the sense that it is conceptualised as an entirely individual-family matter. Thus, although Chema is displeased with the neoliberal PP government in Madrid, by way of his argument he adopts the basic premises of neoliberal rationality. He is displeased with not being able to choose, but he does not reject choice.

Another key point in Chema's discourse is his comparison between 'freedom of choice' and 'freedom'. When asked by the interviewer about 'freedom of choice' he replies: *'I could never say "Freedom, hey no, no, not freedom of centre"'*. With this response, he is equating 'freedom' with 'freedom of choice', thus tracing a hegemonic equivalence (Laclau, 2005). This equivalence makes one think that taking a stance against 'freedom of choice' means being against 'freedom', that both notions are thus the same. In the same line, Chema even slips the idea that zonification models have authoritarian connotations when he states: *'you assign me this centre here... hey, no'* or when he uses the verb *'forve'*. In both moments, he is using imperative verbs with negative connotations. Thus, he understands that the non-provision of options is an imposition to go to a private school. As Brown (2019) explains, a key idea of the neoliberal discourse, which is also the seed of Alt right discourse, is that any state intervention is a totalitarian imposition contrary to freedom. This superficial conception of freedom seems to be the basis of Chema's arguments. We insist, however, that neoliberal rationality coexists with the demand for more funding for

public schools in Chema's discourse, as we have shown before. This example of interdiscursivity (Faiclough, 1999) brings us to the following reflection: the demand for more public funding for public education — a centrepiece of social-democratic discourse— on its own is not enough to counteract the neoliberal governmentality of school choice. As we see in this example, an assemblage between both discourses may even reinforce school choice in the way it finds an ally argument in the social democratic demands for more funding.

José, who holds an academic position at university, is the father of two daughters. They live in Pozuelo, like Paloma. At one point in the interview while talking about bilingual programmes¹⁰ in the Community of Madrid, José makes a similar argument to Chema:

Excerpt 7. 'The whole range of choices may not be possible'.

José: now the choice is, now in fact it would be more difficult... it's more work for a parent, a family to think that they don't want a bilingual education for their child.

Interviewer: ok

José: for example, in Pozuelo.

Interviewer: mhm

José: You know, for example, in Pozuelo, it would really be... no no, if I don't want them to go bilingual because I don't like it or because I'm not interested, or because I already taught them the second language in another way, well... it's probably not the closest public school to their home.

Interviewer: ok

José: it's probably not where his friends from the neighbourhood go, it's not the one he would have liked because he likes more... whatever, the facilities, the curriculum, the pedagogical tradition, you know? they don't choose. And concertado? I don't think there are any selling themselves as providing a mainly monolingual education in Spanish. Choice, there is no choice ((he chuckles)).

¹⁰ 50.4 % of public primary schools and 63.6 % of public secondary schools are part of the Spanish-English bilingualism programme (Comunidad de Madrid, 2021).

Interviewer: But should there be, does the right to choose need to be guaranteed?

José: ((unintelligible)) um... yes, but you also have to manage resources, don't you?

Interviewer: mhm

José: I mean, it's not easy to say, of course it's not... not all... the whole range of possible choices may not be funded or may not be available everywhere... limited resources.

In this extract José blames the lack of plurality of school choice on the expansion of bilingual schools. It is worth highlighting his reasoning to justify the potential arguments of families for not wanting bilingual schools (*'because I don't like it or because I'm not interested, or because I already taught them the second language in another way'*) or to choose a certain school (*'the facilities, the curriculum, the pedagogical tradition'*). Like Chema, with this reasoning he is equating the legitimacy of any individual motivation, again reproducing the neoliberal grammar of what Žižek (2008) calls “pluralist liberalism”. In this way, we see again that the school choice effectively makes parents naturalize an understanding of education as an individual-family matter, and as such, any option is considered legitimate. Here, therefore, we identify the traces of neoliberal rationality. As a result of his reasoning, José reaches a dead end: although he is in favour of plurality in the supply, he understands that public resources are limited and is unable to provide a solution to this impasse.

At another point in the interview, José, in line with Lucía (excerpt 4), points out that choice is mediated by family resources, that is, by social class. He says:

Excerpt 8. 'People who can choose, choose'.

José: People who can choose, you know, so if you... you choose, I choose, well, to send my son or my daughter to a school in a... a school that is outside my neighbourhood, far from my home, public or private, that means I have to... the logistics to get him or her, to get him or her there every day or to pay for the school bus.

With these words, José exposes a certain amount of concern with inequality. In this way, he exposes his political affinity with a rationality closer to the social democratic discourse.

However, as we saw through his words in excerpt 7, this concern does not hinder his adoption of the basic premises of neoliberal discourse. Incluir referencia a interdiscursividad. Nos situamos así ante otra muestra de interdiscursividad, ya que como veíamos en la sección anterior, José asume algunos razonamientos propios del discurso neoliberal.

Both Chema and José trust in the merits of the 'plurality of the educational offer', which is a basic principle of the neoliberal rationality in the field of education. Their stance resonates with the discourse of the PP of Madrid, whose regulation on freedom of school choice establishes 'the plurality of the educational offer' as one of the main principles (article 2c. of the *Decree 29/2013 on Freedom of Choice of 2013*). We understand, therefore, that their stance, despite presenting certain tensions and pointing to the limits of parental choice Madrid, is built based on a frame (Lakoff, 2004) of the market, which is unleashed by the technology of choice and which functions as the primordial organiser, whether consciously or unconsciously. Thus, even if they explicitly position themselves against the PP discourse, they are actually adopting its frame in practice. In doing so, they also take on the discourse of liberal pluralism and conceptualise education as an individual-family matter, diluting it as a collective-community issue.

Rosa: breaking the neoliberal frame from working-class identity

El tercer posicionamiento que identificamos es el de Rosa. Rosa works as a janitor in her neighbourhood and has a son and a stepdaughter —her current partner's daughter— who attended the Secondary Public School Kairós. Kairós was a public Secondary School located in a middle-income neighbourhood of Madrid that was closed by the decision of the Regional Ministry of Education in 2017, who alleged low student enrolment. However, Rosa considered this closure to be part of the Madrid government's policy to dismantle the public network and framed it within a discourse of class struggle:

A diferencia de los otros dos, Rosa elabora su posicionamiento desde su autoidentificación en la clase trabajadora. Desplegando un marco de lucha de clases, se posiciona en contra de la

lógica de distinción que identifica en la elección.

Excerpt 9. 'You are sheep, you have no right to anything'.

Interviewer: You were telling me about freedom of school choice...

Rosa: there is none. There is no freedom of choice. It's all based on... that is, on... putting people where I want to, how I want them, you are sheep, you have no right to anything. We're putting you in... now, where there are twenty, we're going to put thirty. And that's it. And study the minimum, and no... and that's it. We are... well, our children have no opportunities. They are destroying public education, they are destroying healthcare, they are destroying everything. But I'm not talking about a specific group of politicians, I mean, I'm talking in general. In other words, they are throwing everything down the drain, and workers will be workers all our life, and the rich will always be rich, all their life.

Rosa's discourse is a torrent of outrage. When asked about freedom of choice, rather than offering a concise answer, she constructs a narrative of injustice and inequality where *'workers will be workers all our life, and the rich will always be rich'*. She thus establishes a frame (Lakoff, 2004) of class struggle (workers *versus* the rich), wherein she situates herself as part of the working class. It is a frame built up through an they/us polarisation (Laclau & Mouffe, 1985), frequent in political discourses. Within this frame, the lack of choice is part of a broader picture of denial of rights (Rosa mentions *'public education'* and *'health care'*) and the dismantling of public services (*'where there are twenty, we're going to put thirty'*). Moreover, in this frame workers are expected to be submissive (*'sheep'*) and accept this situation, as Rosa angrily states. Within this frame, school is no longer a space for equal opportunities: *'our children'* —i.e., the children of the working class— go to school to *'study the minimum'*, says Rosa indignantly. Whereas José and Chema identified an unfulfilled promise, the frame of the class struggle allows Rosa to identify in the election a mechanism that further reinforces social class inequality.

At another point in the interview, also within this class struggle frame, Rosa negatively evaluates school choice as a device of social distinction. She uses her sister as an example:

Excerpt 10. 'Although she's my sister, she's very elitist'.

Rosa: although she is my sister, she's very elitist. She couldn't have her children in a public school with people, with people that aren't like them. After all my brother-in-law is a janitor, like me, you know? Well, they live on {unintelligible} street, but he's a janitor, and my sister is a telephone operator. But I cannot allow my daughter to be with a South American boy. So, I'm telling you this, but, she's my sister, and this is not going to get out... ((laughs))

Interviewer: it's anonymous.

Rosa: because if it's not... ((laughs)) my children have spent time with all types of races, cultures, and education. There have been Moor children, there have been Christian children, there have been... people of colour. That school [Kairós] was multicultural.

In this excerpt 10, Rosa takes a stance (Du Bois, 2007) against the behaviour of her sister. She accuses her of being '*elitist*' for having chosen a '*concertado*' school as a strategy of class distinction (to avoid '*people that aren't like them*') and to avoid immigrant pupils ('*I can't allow my daughter to be with a South American boy*'). Thus, Rosa explicitly takes a stance in favour of multicultural education. Here, Rosa is drawing an equivalence (Laclau & Mouffe, 1985) between her class identity and immigrant identity. With this equivalence, she positions herself in favour of multicultural education and associates her sister's elitist attitude with other social classes, perhaps with the '*rich*' she described in excerpt 9. Finally, through Rosa's reference to her sister's and brother-in-law's jobs we can infer that Rosa negatively evaluates their behaviour as unbecoming of their socio-economic class, and perhaps as a class betrayal.

Rosa's discourse, nearly unique among the mothers interviewed for this study, seems particularly relevant because it provides us with significant reflections. Firstly, it reveals a clear limit of neoliberal governmentality: school choice does not achieve to subjectify her as an *entrepreneur of the self*, that is, as a consumer of education. On the contrary, she takes a stance against that logic and the fears of the middle classes regarding choice (Ball, 2006) through the

example of her sister. Therefore, when asked about school choice, rather than a description of her practices—as Paloma offered in excerpts 1 and 2— she offers a testimony of injustice and outrage. Secondly, we observe that Rosa does not feel interpellated by this rationality because her life experience—including her experience as a Kairos' mother— as a working-class mother and a subject denied rights moves her to deploy a frame of class struggle. Through this frame, she places herself alongside the groups that generally suffer the consequences of school segregation. She thus appeals to a 'multicultural' educational model that moves away from the individual-family conception—in contrast to those we clearly identified in Chema and José's stances.

Conclusion

In this article, we have provided an analytical framework specifically designed to trace in interview data the tensions of mothers' discourses in relation to school choice. This analytical framework combines the governmentality approach with a set of tools taken from discourse studies. We have applied this analytical framework to fragments of interviews with mothers whose children attend public schools in the Madrid community. Thus, as a secondary objective, we have presented three types of mothers' stances regarding choice in the context of Madrid. Each of these stances reflects a different type of tension regarding school choice.

Firstly, and in line with other studies (Oría et al., 2007; Reay et al., 2011; Wilkins, 2010, 2014), Lucía and Paloma take an ambivalent stance toward school choice. The meaning of this dilemma, however, is arguable. On the one hand, it seems to reflect a limit of neoliberal governmentality: competition rationality has not subjectified them successfully as convinced entrepreneurs of themselves in that they do not share individualistic ethics of choice. But on the other hand, their ethical disconformity with school choice has not prevented them from choosing based on individualistic criteria. Unlike Friedman and Figar, their individualistic motivations are not rooted on a belief in competition, but rather on fear to the other. We could

say that, in a sign of interdiscursivity (Fairclough, 1993), neoliberal governmentality interacts with other discourses present in the social space that also are based on inequality. In this case, it interacts with racist and classist discourses to guide Lucia and Paloma's choices. Thus, their show of concern for inequality and shame/guilt for their decisions serves to construct a positive "face" of themselves, that is, it serves them to offer a more acceptable image of the motivations behind their choice. In other words, their own self-criticism functions as a plea for a truce with anyone who may label them as classist or racist.

Chema's and José' stance reveals a second tension. In this case, it is not a dilemma in their subjectivation, but instead a tension in freedom of choice itself: to them, it is an unfulfilled promise. In their discourse, they uncritically assume the fundamental premises of neoliberal discourse in education: firstly, that plurality of supply must be guaranteed, and secondly, that education is an individual-family matter. Like in Paloma and Lucía's responses, choice activates a conceptualisation of education as an individual-family matter in their discourse. Any understanding of education as a community-collective matter is diluted and even suggested to be authoritarian. A crucial point of their stance is that it can coexist with some social democratic demands, such as greater public funding.

Finally, in Rosa's voice, we identify a third stance with very different characteristics. Through the frame of class struggle, Rosa is not only not interpellated by neoliberal governmentality as a consumer, but she also confronts it. She frames her experience of not being able to choose —because her chosen option, the Secondary School Kairós, was closed— within a collective narrative of denial of social rights for the working and migrant classes. In this way, Rosa points to the classic capital-labour (rich versus workers) contradiction on which the capitalist order is configured. In this way, her discourse evokes a Marxist framework based on the principle of universal equality, the rights of the dispossessed, and the class struggle. Asked about choice, she takes a stance of outright rejection of the understanding of education as an individual means of social distinction, using the example of her own sister. We draw the

following lesson from Rosa's words: class identity emerges as the only place of enunciation from which it is possible to escape the market frame and, thus, to escape neoliberal governmentality. This is due to the grammar of universal equality and the language of rights on which this identity is based. From this place, Rosa creates a chain of equivalences with other oppressed groups, such as immigrant communities.

Taken together, these three stances reveal that neoliberal governmentality does not generate harmonious *entrepreneurs of self* among mothers. The combination of these tools has allowed us to develop a fine-grained analysis of mothers' discourse regarding school choice. Unlike the seamless neoliberal discourse posed by Milton Friedman or Lucía Figar, the neoliberal rationality emerges in mothers' discourse in a tangled way with other discourses in a sample of interdiscursivity (Fairclough, 1993), thus generating contradictory stances. In particular, the stance taking analysis (Du Bois, 2007), by focusing on the way interviewees evaluate the object they are speaking about—in this case, freedom of school choice and their choice practices—has allowed us to show that the individualistic logic of neoliberal governmentality does not require the ethical commitment of mothers with competition to guide their practices. Additionally, the frame analysis (Lakoff, 2004, 2006) has allowed us to identify a counter-hegemonic that escapes neoliberal rationality. This discourse is elaborated on a rights-based discursive frame and anchored in working-class identity.

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